

Physicochemical Standardization and TLC Analysis of In-House and Marketed *Ocimum sanctum* Homeopathic Mother Tincture Using Standard Ursolic Acid

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ABSTRACT

In India, Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) is a tonic for the body, mind and spirit that offers solutions to many modern-day health problems. Tulsi is best examples of holistic lifestyle approach to health. The objective of this work is to report physicochemical standardisation of the homeopathic *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture (OSMT). To assess the quality difference between In-house and marketed brand of *Ocimum sanctum* homeopathic mother tincture was chosen for their evaluation. Physicochemical properties such as weight per ml, total solid content, alcohol content, refractive index, pH value & λ max was performed. Furthermore, the chemical evaluation of OSMT by thin layer chromatography (TLC) and UV-Vis spectrophotometry was done. In the present study, ursolic acid as chemical markers used for characterization. Precoated silica gel plates were used as stationary phase & separation was achieved using toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid: (7:3:1 v/v/v) as mobile phase. The presence of ursolic acid was confirmed by TLC with Rf value 0.72 in both In-house and marketed MT. The concentrations of ursolic Acid in In-house & marketed *Ocimum* mother tincture was found to be 6.771 and 1.762 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. UV- VIS absorption spectrum of ursolic acid was characterized by a large peak around 273 nm in both OSMT. TPC & TFC was also determined. Our study provides the physicochemical standards for the drug & OSMT along with simple analytical technique. It establishes ursolic acid as chemical marker corresponding its biological activity of homeopathic mother tincture of *Ocimum sanctum*.

Keywords: Homeopathic drug & mother tincture standardization: HPTLC ursolic acid, *Ocimum sanctum*

INTRODUCTION

Due to its various medicinal properties, tulsi, also known as *Ocimum sanctum* L. or *Ocimum tenuiflorum*, has been widely used in Ayurveda for thousands of years. Tulsi is One of the most beloved health-promoting herbs of the Asian region also known as the Queen of Herbs. Tulsi, frequently referred to as the sacred basil, is well known for its religious and spiritual sacredness, as Charaka states in the Charaka Samhita. It plays an important role in the traditional Unani and Ayurvedic systems of herbal medicine and holistic health.¹ As an adaptogen, tulsi helps the body adjust to stress by balancing various bodily functions. It is considered a sort of "elixir of life" in Ayurveda and is thought to extend life because of its potent aroma and astringent taste.² Ayurvedic

treatments for common colds, headaches, stomach issues, inflammation, heart disease, and malaria often use tulsi extracts. *O. sanctum* L. is traditionally consumed in a variety of ways, including fresh leaves, dried powder, and herbal tea. To keep insects away, dried Tulsi leaves have been mixed with grains for ages.^{3,4}

The erect, heavily branching shrub *Ocimum sanctum* L. (tulsi) grows to a height of 30 to 60 cm. Hairy stems with leaves that are either green or purple in color and have a pungent aroma. Its petiole is 5 cm long. Purplish flowers are arranged in tight whorls in elongated racemes.^{5,6} Tulsi is a widely grown plant that is indigenous to the tropics of the world. It is grown for its essential oil as well as for religious and therapeutic purposes. In many Hindu religious

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traditions, tulsi is a significant symbol that is associated with a goddess figure. In Sanskrit, "Tulsi" signifies "the incomparable one." A Tulsi plant's being represents a Hindu family's religious inclinations.^{7,8} The World Health Organization estimates that 70–80% of people worldwide, particularly in developing countries, get their basic medical care from complementary and alternative therapies like homeopathy, siddha, and ayurveda.⁹ The medical method known as homeopathy has a century-old history and operates on the tenet of "Similia Similibus Curentur." It is among the most effective holistic treatments. In their daily work, homeopathic practitioners frequently administer mother tinctures as medicinal agents. These medications come in a variety of combination formulas, dilutions, mother tinctures, and biochemicals.¹⁰

Mother Tinctures

The crude drug is macerated, or dissolved, in alcohol and water to create the mother tinctures. The Greek letter theta (θ) or the letter "Q" are used to represent them (Banerjee, D.D., 2006). (W.A. Dewey, 1998). It is a precisely measured mixture of a certain amount of alcohol and a plant extract. Mother tinctures are frequently used to treat a range of allergies, infections, toxicities, autoimmune diseases, chronic illnesses, and acute illnesses because of their rapid medicinal action and high herbal extract potency.¹¹

The amount of crude drug in a mother tincture determines its drug strength. Different standard methods can be used to evaluate the mother tincture's quality.^{12,13}

To satisfy specific requirements for the finished product, the manufacturing industry depends on both qualitative and quantitative analysis of raw materials. Mother tinctures can undergo both qualitative and quantitative investigation to assess the preparation's identification, stability, and purity.¹⁴ Analyses of alcohol content, weight per milliliter, pH, total solids, chromatography, spectrophotometry for λ max analysis, and other factors are used to evaluate the quality of mother tinctures.¹⁵ Therefore, the objective of this research is to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the quality standards of

both in -house and commercially available homeopathic mother tinctures. It covers formulation quality control as well as manufacturing procedures including raw material analysis and the end-product manufacturing. It also involves systematically ensuring and evaluating the items' quality, understanding their safety profiles, and maintaining their purity while consulting a pharmacopeial monograph.¹⁶

As of at present, no *Ocimum MQ* standard specifications have been established for assessing the potencies and pharmacological strength of homeopathic remedies. The final product's quality and dependability are enhanced by careful attention to detail at every stage of production. Therefore, the present research aims to evaluate the quality of marketed brands and in-house made *Ocimum* homeopathic mother tincture.^{17,18}

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of The Raw Drug And Mother Tincture

The raw drug *Ocimum sanctum* was collected from wild in the flowering stage from Shirpur, Dhule Maharashtra on 15 September 2023 (Voucher number: 0183). The plants were taxonomically authenticated by the field botanist at the SSVPS Science college Dhule Maharashtra. The sun-dried plants were collected for the drug preparation. Then, they were shade-dried for 24 h and have been used as the raw drug for further study. The marketed brand of *Ocimum* mother tincture is collected for the study.

Experimental procedures

Morphological Characteristics & Physico-Chemical Analysis Of *Ocimum Sanctum* Crude Drugs

Morphological characteristics of *Ocimum sanctum* was carry out as per standard protocol including colour, odour, taste, lamina, leaf margin, height etc. Physical parameter including ash values, extractives values, LOD etc. were determined.

Ash Value

Ash is used for removing any organic debris that can impede the identification of inorganic elements.

Using methods stated, the total ash, acid-insoluble ash, and water-soluble ash of *Ocimum sanctum* leaves were determined.

Determination of Total Ash Value

In a tared platinum crucible, 3 grams of precisely weighed air-dried leaves were taken out. At the bottom of the platinum crucible, the drug material was evenly distributed in a fine layer. This platinum crucible containing the drug was stored for ignition in a muffle furnace. The furnace's temperature was progressively raised to 450°C until the drug was completely ignited and white ash was produced. After that, the crucible was removed from the furnace, allowed to cool, and weighed. Three duplicates of the determination were made. The weight of the crucible containing the drug powder prior to ignition was subtracted from the weight of the crucible containing the drug ash following ignition to determine the total amount of ash. The percentage of total ash was computed using the medication that had been air-dried.¹⁹

Total ash (%) = $\frac{\text{Weight of ash} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$

Acid Insoluble Ash

For five minutes, 25 millilitres of 2N hydrochloric acid were used to boil the ash produced by the total ash method. After being collected on ash less filter paper (Whatman paper no. 40), insoluble material was cleaned with hot water. The substance that was retained on the filter paper was then burned and weighed with the filter paper.

Using the air-dried material as a reference, the percentage of acid-insoluble ash was determined.

Water Soluble Ash

The ash obtained from total ash was boiled with 25 ml water for 5 min. The complete ash was ignited for five minutes with twenty-five milliliters of water. Ashless filter paper was used to collect all insoluble material, which was then cleaned with hot water and burned for 15 minutes at a temperature no higher than 450°C. By deducting the weight of insoluble materials from the weight of

total ash, the percentage of water-soluble ash was determined. Water-soluble ash is represented by the weight differential. Using the air-dried medication as a reference, the percentage of water-soluble ash was determined.

Total ash (%) = $\frac{\text{Weight of ash} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$

Loss On Drying (LOD)

In brief, a silica crucible containing 5 g of air-dried medication was used to estimate the LOD. Prior to that, the crucible was cleaned, dried, and its empty weight was recorded. A thin, even layer of the powder was applied. After that, the crucible was put in an oven set to 105°C. The weight of the cooled crucible plus powder was recorded after the powder was dried for four hours and allowed to cool to room temperature in a desiccator.

LOD = $\frac{\text{weight of sample before dry} - \text{weight of sample after dry}}{\text{weight of sample before dry}} \times 100$

Preparation of *In-House Mother Tincture*

Selection of Plant Material:

Obtain fresh or dried plant material of *Ocimum sanctum* (holy basil). Ensure that the collected plant material is of good quality and free from contaminants.

Mother Tincture

Follow the same steps as for the crude drug extract preparation but adjust the concentration of the extract in the final solvent to achieve the desired strength suitable for use as a mother tincture. Typically, a mother tincture contains 1-part plant material to 10 parts solvent by weight. Store the mother tincture in airtight containers away from light, heat, and moisture.²⁰ Perform quality control tests such as phytochemical screening, chromatographic analysis, and assays for marker compounds to ensure the consistency, potency, and quality of mother tincture.

Standardization of *In-House* and Marketed Mother Tincture Of *Ocimum Sanctum*

The mother tincture was standardized in order to compare its physicochemical characteristics, including weight per milliliter, total solid content, alcohol content, refractive index, pH value, and λ max, as well as its organoleptic characteristics, including color, odor, and taste.^{21,22}

Specific Gravity

Weigh the empty bottle accurately and record the weight. Fill the pycnometer with the liquid sample marketed *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture and In-house mother tincture up to the brim. Make sure there are no air bubbles trapped inside the liquid. Weigh the filled pycnometer accurately using the same balance. Record this weight. Subtract the weight of the empty pycnometer from the weight of the filled pycnometer to determine the weight of the liquid sample. Divide the weight of the liquid sample by the weight of an equal volume of water at the same temperature to calculate the specific gravity.²³

Specific gravity = weight of liquid / weight of equal volume of water

It's essential to conduct measurements at a consistent temperature, as specific gravity is temperature dependent. If the measurements are taken at a different temperature from the reference temperature (usually 20°C), a temperature correction may be necessary.

pH Value

Dilute the marketed and In-house *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture with distilled water if necessary to obtain a suitable concentration for measurement. Immerse the electrode of the pH meter previously calibrated using standard buffer solutions at pH, into the sample solution. Allow the pH meter to stabilize, then record the pH value indicated on the meter. Rinse the electrode of the pH meter with distilled water after use to prevent contamination.

Total Solid Content

Weigh a clean, dry, and pre-weighed evaporating dish or crucible accurately using an analytical balance. Record the weight as W_1 . Pour a known volume of the marketed and In-house *Ocimum sanctum* mother

tincture into the pre-weighed dish or crucible. Place the dish or crucible containing the sample on a hot plate or in an oven set to a specific temperature (e.g., 105°C) to evaporate the solvent. Continue heating the sample until all the solvent has evaporated, leaving behind the solid residues. Ensure complete dryness by heating the sample for a sufficient duration. Allow the dish or crucible with the dried residues to cool in a desiccator to prevent moisture absorption. Once cooled, re-weigh the dish or crucible with the residues accurately. Record the weight as W_2 .²⁴

$$\text{Total Solid Content (\%)} = (W_2 - W_1) / W_1 \times 100$$

Refractive Index

Place a few drops of marketed and In-house *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture onto the surface of the prism or sample well of the refractometer. Ensure that the sample covers the entire surface uniformly to avoid air bubbles. Close the prism cover or lower the arm of the refractometer to bring the sample into contact with the prism. Look through the eyepiece or digital display of the refractometer and adjust the focus until the boundary between light and dark areas (the boundary line) is sharp and distinct. Take the reading of the refractive index directly from the scale or digital display of the refractometer. After measurement, clean the prism or sample well of the refractometer with a suitable solvent (e.g., ethanol) and a soft cloth to remove any residue from the previous sample.

Alcohol Content

The usual method should be used to determine the alcohol concentration in homeopathic tinctures. It is made up of a 500 ml round-bottom flask that is connected to a vertical condenser and has a distillation head with a steam trap. The latter has a tapered tube attached to its lower portion that transports the distillate into a 100 ml volumetric flask. During the distillation process, the volumetric flask is submerged in a water-ice mixture. To lessen the possibility of any dissolved materials charring, a disc with a circular opening 6 cm in diameter is positioned beneath the flask. Pour 25.0 milliliters of the 25°-measured tincture into the distillation flask. Use 100–150 milliliters of water to dilute. Connect the condenser and distillation head. Fill a 100 ml volumetric flask

with at least 90 ml of the distillate after it has been distilled. Set the temperature to 25° and dilute with 100 ml of water at the same temperature. Using a pycnometer or a specific gravity bottle, find the specific gravity at 25°. Determine the alcohol's v/v % using the table.²⁴

Quantitative Estimations:

Using a conventional procedure, a quantitative measurement of the mother tincture was conducted to ascertain the amount of total phenolics and flavonoid content. Total flavonoid content by aluminum chloride and 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine with quercetin as an internal standard, and total phenolic contents by Folin-ciocalteu technique with gallic acid as an internal standard (Sadasivam, S. and Manickam 1996).

Determination Of Total Phenolic Content (TPC)

The Folin–Ciocalteu colorimetric method, as described by, was used to determine the mother tincture's total phenolic contents (TPC). with a few changes. 10 milligrams of gallic acid were dissolved in 10 mL of methanol (1 mg/mL) to produce the standard gallic acid solution and sample. Gallic acid solutions in methanol at different strengths (25, 50, 75, and 100 µg/mL) were marketed, and an *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture was made internally using the stock solution. Five milliliters of 10% Folin–Ciocalteu reagent (FCR) and four milliliters of 7% Na₂CO₃ were added to each concentration, resulting in a final volume of ten milliliters. As a result, the resulting blue mixture was thoroughly agitated before being incubated in a water bath at 40°C for 30 minutes. The absorbance was then measured against a blank at 760 nm. Phenols in plant extracts are oxidized by the FCR reagent, turning them dark blue, which is then detected using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. Every experiment was run in triplicate, and the calibration curve was plotted using the average absorbance readings at various gallic acid doses.²⁵

Determining of Flavonoid Content

Total flavonoid contents in the marketed and In-house *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture was determined by aluminum chloride colorimetric assay. Stock solution (10 mg/mL) of quercetin was prepared by dissolving

10 mg of quercetin in 10 mL of methanol. Standard solution was diluted serially to make various concentrations of 10-50 µg/mL solutions. 1 mL quercetin of each concentration was added to the test tube containing 4 mL of distilled water. At the same time, 0.3 mL of 5% NaNO₂ was added to the test tube and 0.3 mL of 10% AlCl₃ after 5 min. then, 2 mL of 1 M NaOH was added to the mixture after 6 min. the volume of the mixture was made 10 mL by immediately adding 4.4 mL of distilled water. The total flavonoids content was expressed as quercetin equivalents using the linear equation based on the calibration curve.²⁵

TLC Study Of *In-House* And Marketed *Ocimum* Mother Tincture

Several solvent systems comprising the various proportion of nonpolar to polar solvent were tried for the optimization of better resolution. example Ethyl acetate: methanol: water (5:3:2.2, v/v/v) ; Ethyl acetate: formic acid: acetic acid: water (4:1:3:2 v/v/v); Chloroform: methanol: water (6:2:2 v/v/v); Toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid: (7:3:1 v/v/v) ; Toluene: ethyl acetate: diethylamine (7:2:1 v/v/v); Toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid (6:3.5:0.5 v/v/v) ; Pet ether: acetone (08:02 v/v/v); Hexane: ethyl acetate (7.5: 2.5 v/v/v); Toluene: ethyl acetate: glacial acetic acid (9:1:0.4 v/v/v);, Finally Better resolution was obtained in toluene: ethyl acetate: formic acid: (7:3:1 v/v/v). Anisaldehyde sulfuric acid reagent was used as spraying reagent. with heated in oven at 105° for 2-5 min. Ursolic acid was used as terpenoids as standard marker compound.²⁶

Preparation of Stock Standard Solution

Stock standard solution of was prepared by dissolving 5 mg of ursolic acid into 50 mL of volumetric flask consisting of methanol sonicated for 10 min to obtain the concentration of 100 µg/mL.

Determination of Λ Max & Linearity Studies

1 mL ursolic acid was transferred from standard stock solution into 10 mL calibrated flask and the volume was adjusted to the mark with same to obtain the concentration of 10 µg/mL. The resulting solution was scanned in UV range 800-200 nm with methanol as blank. Maximum absorbance was recorded at 273 nm

depicted. Ursolic Acid in the range 1 – 5 mL from the stock standard solution were moved into series of five separate 10 mL of calibrated flask. The volume was adjusted to the mark with same to obtain the concentrations in the range of 10-50 µg/mL. To establish the linear relationship between ursolic acid concentrations and responses the calibration curves were constructed by plotting concentrations *versus* absorbance in the results obtained and calibration curves are presented.

Quantification of Ursolic Acid in Mother Tincture

A linear regression equation of the calibration curve of working standard solutions was used to determine the amount of ursolic acid. Three separate measurements of the amount of ursolic acid in the in-house and marketed mother tincture sample were made, and the results were shown as milligrams per 100 g of the crude medication. Together with their SD values, the contents were displayed. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test was used to analyze the differences in ursolic acid contents across the sample groups. A value of $P < 0.05$ was established for the statistical significance of each tested group.²⁷

RESULTS

Morphology of *Ocimum Sanctum*

Ocimum sanctum has a sweet, slightly spicy aroma with light pungent and slight bitter in taste. The leaves are ovate to lanceolate with lamina length 3 to 5 cm. The leaf margins are entire or slightly serrated. Typically, the plant reaches a height of 30 to 60 cm. Depending on the cultivar, leaves can be either green or purple, while stems are often green. Additionally, the stems are quadrangular and have a tendency to stay green and purple.

Physicochemical Study of Raw Drug

The physicochemical parameters of raw *Ocimum* drugs are tabulated in Table 1. The moisture content was found to be around 8–9% w/w. The total ash value was around 6.5-7% w/w. This assumption may further be justified by the fact that the sample has considerable acid-insoluble ash value i.e 1.98 % w/w. The overall result has been summarised in the following table.

Table 1. Physicochemical study of raw *Ocimum* drug

Parameters	Quantitative values % w/w
Foreign matter	0.05-0.1
Loss on drying at 105°C	8-9
Total Ash value	6.5-7
Acid-insoluble ash	1.78-1.98
Water-insoluble ash	6.80-7.03
Water soluble extractive value	5.9-6.7
Alcohol soluble extractive value	4.6-5.1
Ether soluble extractive value	3.3-3.9

Preparation and Standardization Of *In-House* & Marketed *Ocimum Sanctum* Mother Tincture (OSMT)

Organoleptic and physicochemical properties such as appearance, colour, odour, density, dry residue,

alcohol content, and chemical marker was evaluated. The specific gravity of mother tincture was found be below 1. Table.2

Table. 2: Physicochemical Data Of *In-House* & Marketed *Ocimum Sanctum* Mother Tincture

Parameters	<i>In-house</i> <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (IH-OSMT)	Marketed <i>Ocimum sanctum</i> (M-OSMT)
Drug strength	1/10	1/10
Appearance	Green Liquid	Green Liquid
Colour	Dark Green	Light Green

Odour	Spicy, & Slightly Peppery	Sweet, Spicy, & Slightly Peppery
Wt.per/ml	0.850±0.0011	0.780±0.0036
Specific Gravity	0.9230	0.9508
pH value	6.0 pH	6.1 pH
Total Solid Content	1.1 % w/w	1.5 % w/w
Refractive Index	1.399	1.419
Alcohol Content	86.1 %v/v	85.2% v/v
Sediment	Nil	Nil
λmax	273 nm	273 nm
TPC (ug/10ml)	6.90	5.61
TFC (ug/10ml)	8.41	6.87

Fingerprinting Of Mother Tincture

Figure 1. Comparative Thin Layer Chromatography of In-House and Marketed Ocimum Mother Tincture Under 254 Nm Ultraviolet Light

Fingerprinting profiling of the phytochemical components of the *In-house* & marketed *Ocimum* MT were performed using HPTLC analysis WIN CATS software along with standard reference compounds ursolic acid. Fig.1-4 & Table 3.

Quantification of Ursolic Acid In *In-House* & Marketed Mother Tincture

A linear regression equation of the calibration curve of working standard solutions was used to determine the amount of ursolic acid. The amount of ursolic acid

in the mother tincture that was sold and marketed and in-house was measured three times and presented as milligrams per 100 milliliters. Together with their SD values, the contents were displayed. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's multiple comparison post hoc test was used to analyse the differences in ursolic acid contents across the sample groups. A value of $P < 0.05$ was established for the statistical significance of each tested group. The concentrations of ursolic Acid in *In-house* & marketed *Ocimum* mother tincture was found to be 6.771 and 4.762 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively.

Figure 2: 3-D HPTLC Chromatogram Of Marketed And In-House Mother Tincture

Figure 3. HPTLC Spectral Chromatogram of Marketed and In-House Mother Tincture Displaying Ursolic Acid

Table 3. Rf values of the spots of In-house and marketed mother tinctures at 254 & 366 nm

Detector @ 254 nm			Detector @ 366 nm		
Max Rf Marketed MT	Color	In-house MT	Max Rf Marketed MT	Color	In-house MT
0.02		0.02	0.05		0.04
0.08	Pale blue	0.08	0.09	Blue	0.09
0.10	Pale blue	0.11	0.18	Green	0.17
0.33	Pale green	0.23	0.39	Pink	0.27
0.37	Green	0.31	0.39	Green	0.35
0.45	Dark green	0.46	0.48		0.47

0.55	Faint Violet	0.53	0.51	Pink	0.55
0.63	Violet	0.66	0.69	Pink	0.68
0.72	Pinkish	0.72	0.72	Violet	0.72
0.86	Pinkish Violet	0.89	0.89	Violet	0.84
0.95	Dark green	0.93	0.98	Green	0.95

Figure 4. Overlay UV Spectrum Of IHMT: In-House Ocimum Mother Tincture; MMT: Marketed Mother Tincture & UA: Ursolic Acid

DISCUSSION

Morphology Of *Ocimum Sanctum*

Overall, the unique morphological features of *Ocimum sanctum*, such as its aromatic nature, distinct leaf shape, quadrangular stems, and floral arrangement, make it an easily identifiable and valuable herb in both medicinal and culinary applications.

The Physicochemical Study of Raw *Ocimum Sanctum* Drug

Physicochemical analysis is an essential aspect of evaluating the quality, purity, and standardization of herbal drugs. These parameters help in assessing the stability, composition, and authenticity of the raw drug.

Relatively low value of moisture content indicates that the plant material used has undergone sun and shade-drying before analysis thereby preventing microbial growth and ensuring the shelf life and stability of the raw drug. The total ash value was reflecting the presence of inorganic components, including minerals, metals, silica, and silicates. The

acid-insoluble ash indicating the proportion of silica and silicates, which may originate from the plant itself or contamination from external sources such as soil or dust. The extractive values of *Ocimum sanctum* in different solvents indicates that polar solvents can extract a higher amount of bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, polyphenols, and glycosides, compared to non-polar solvents.

Preparation and Standardization Of In-House & Marketed *Ocimum Sanctum* Mother Tincture (OSMT)

The preparation and standardization of homeopathic mother tinctures (MT) involve the evaluation of organoleptic and physicochemical properties to ensure consistency, efficacy, and compliance with standard pharmacopeial guidelines such as the Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia of India (HPI). This study compared the in-house prepared mother tincture (IHMT) with marketed OSMT (MOSMT), assessing various quality parameters.

Colour variations in different mother tinctures were observed, influenced by factors such as harvest time, rainfall, and chlorophyll concentration. Higher

chlorophyll content at the time of harvest resulted in a greener tincture. Specific gravity was found to be below 1, indicating the tincture's density is slightly lower than water, a standard feature in ethanol-based preparations. The weight per milliliter (w/ml) of IHMT was greater than MOSMT, suggesting a higher concentration of dissolved solids, which may be an indicator of better extraction efficiency. The solid content of IHMT was close to the standard HPI value, confirming its good quality. The alcohol content of MOSMT was slightly higher than the standard HPI value, ensuring proper preservation and extraction of active constituents. The pH values of all tested tinctures were slightly deviant but remained close to neutral, indicating stability and safety for therapeutic use. Both in-house (IHMT) and marketed (MOSMT) mother tinctures met the quality requirements, with MOSMT exhibiting slightly higher alcohol content while IHMT displayed greater weight per ml and solid content, aligning well with the HPI standards. The physicochemical properties, including colour, odour, alcohol content, and solid residue, confirmed the tinctures' good quality and potential therapeutic efficacy.

Fingerprinting of *Ocimum Sanctum* Mother Tincture (OSMT)

Different solvent systems were tested using a trial-and-error approach to achieve optimal separation of bioactive compounds such as ursolic acid and quercetin. The best separation of bands was achieved using a Toluene: Ethyl Acetate: Formic Acid (7:2:1 v/v/v) solvent system, derivatized with anisaldehyde sulfuric acid. The bands of standard compounds were visualized under UV (254 nm & 366 nm) and white light, confirming their presence. The Retention Factor (*R_f*) of Ursolic Acid was found to be 0.72, confirming its presence in both in-house and marketed OSMT samples. The absorbance spectra were determined using UV-VIS spectroscopy to confirm the presence of ursolic acid in the formulations. The UV-VIS absorption spectrum of ursolic acid displayed a peak at around 273 nm, which is characteristic of its electronic transitions. Overlay spectra revealed differences in peak intensity, suggesting variations in ursolic acid content or its interaction with other phytochemicals.

The TLC fingerprinting and UV-VIS spectral analysis provided a preliminary chemical profiling of *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture. The UV overlay spectra further confirmed the presence and stability of ursolic acid in the formulations. These findings can contribute to homoeopathy and other medicinal systems by ensuring the authenticity and consistency of OSMT preparations.

Quantification Of Ursolic Acid In In-House & Marketed Mother Tincture

The in-house preparation exhibited a notably higher ursolic acid content (6.771 µg/mL) compared to the marketed formulation (4.762 µg/mL). This substantial difference suggests variations in the raw material, extraction techniques, or formulation processes used in both preparations. A higher ursolic acid content in the in-house tincture suggests that it may offer greater therapeutic efficacy, given the well-documented pharmacological benefits of ursolic acid, including its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer properties. However, further studies assessing the bioavailability, stability, and clinical efficacy of both tinctures would be necessary to establish their comparative therapeutic value.

The study highlights the importance of standardizing mother tincture formulations to ensure consistent active constituent levels. Manufacturers should focus on optimizing raw material selection and extraction techniques to maintain higher ursolic acid concentrations in marketed preparations. Future research could explore different standardization approaches and stability-enhancing strategies for improving the consistency and efficacy of *Ocimum* mother tinctures.

CONCLUSION

As per WHO, homoeopathy has grown enormously in the last decade and is now the second most preferred mode of treatment because of little or no side effects at all. *Ocimum* is a herb that has been used for thousands of years as medicine. It primarily affects the neurological and digestive systems. *Ocimum* is used in Ayurveda as a stomachic, anthelmintic, and antipyretic. It also helps with indigestion, enhances taste, and is beneficial for blood and heart conditions. According to certain research, it has anti-

inflammatory, anti-ulcer, heart stimulant, antioxidant, and radical scavenging properties.

Mother tincture HPTLC fingerprint profiles are becoming recognized as a useful technique for characterizing the complex nature of plant constituents. Ursolic acid and quercetin are confirmed by HPTLC fingerprinting analysis, whereas ursolic acid in in-house made homoeopathic mother tincture and market samples is primarily determined by UV spectroscopy analysis. The study's findings could be applied to scientific validation and the development of guidelines for the medication's quality control. We believe our study provides a simple, economical, yet significantly sensitive physicochemical standardisation procedure for the drug *Ocimum*. In conclusion, Overall, *Ocimum sanctum* mother tincture offers a holistic approach to health and wellness, drawing upon the rich tradition of Ayurvedic medicine.

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